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EFFECT OF MACROECONOMIC FACTORS ON STOCK RETURNS OF QUOTED COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The capital market, where stocks are traded, represents a crucial platform for rapid economic development of any nation. Stock returns are a fundamental concept in finance, representing the gain or loss realized by an investor from holding a stock over a specific period. This study examined the effect of macroeconomic factors; interest rate, inflation and exchange rate, on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria for 2015-2024. Interest rate was proxied by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) prime lending rate (PLR), inflation rate was proxied by the CBN year-on-year inflation rate and exchange rate was proxied by the naira to US dollar. The endogenous variable, stock returns was proxied by Dividend-Adjusted Return (DAR). Population of the study comprised of firm listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGXGroup). 27 firms were sampled based on market capitalization as at 31st December, 2024. Employing quantitative longitudinal research design, the study utilized secondary data sourced from the CBN, the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS) as well as the published annual reports of the sampled companies. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, least square regression model and granger causality tests. Findings revealed that both interest rate and exchange rate exhibited a negative and statistically significant relationship with dividend-adjusted returns (DAR) while inflation demonstrated a positive and highly significant effect on stock returns. The study recommended amongst others, that the CBN should adopt a balanced interest rate policy that supports economic stability without stifling equity market growth and maintain inflation within an optimal band through proactive monetary and fiscal coordination to preserve investor purchasing power and market stability. Investors should factor currency risk into their valuation models and consider exposure to export-oriented firms that benefit from naira depreciation.

KEYWORDS: Stock Returns, Market Capitalization, Stock Exchange, Emerging Economies, Market Volatility.

INTRODUCTION

In the global financial landscape, stock markets serve as vital indicators of economic health and investor sentiment. Capital markets, where stocks are traded serve as key vehicles for investment and wealth creation, making the determinants of stock returns a subject of enduring relevance. In emerging economies such as Nigeria, the stock markets play a pivotal role in capital formation, resource allocation, and economic development (Salisu & Lawan, 2018). Across both developed and emerging economies, stock returns are influenced by a range of macroeconomic factors that reflect the broader economic climate. Variables such as interest rates, inflation rate, and exchange rates have been widely studied for their impact on market performance, with evidence suggesting that shifts in these indicators can significantly alter investor behaviour and asset valuations (Fama, 1981; Chen et al., 1986). In developed markets, the transmission mechanisms between macroeconomic policy and stock returns are relatively well understood. However, in emerging economies like Nigeria, these relationships are often more volatile and less predictable due to structural inefficiencies, policy inconsistencies, and external shocks.

Stock returns are a fundamental concept in finance, representing the gain or loss realized by an investor from holding a stock over a specific period. This return is typically expressed as a percentage of the initial investment and is composed of two key components: capital gains, which arise from changes in the stock's market price, and income returns, usually in the form of dividends. Brealey et al. (2020) defined stock return as the total income from an investment, emphasizing that both price appreciation and dividend income must be considered to accurately assess performance. Modigliani and Pogue (1973) describe return as the "reward for investing," highlighting its central role in

evaluating financial decisions.

Scholars measure stock returns using various approaches that reflect both historical performance and investor gains. Such measures include Dividend-Adjusted Return (DAR) also known as total return, Market Returns (index-based) and Stock Price Changes. The DAR was adopted by this study as a measure of the endogenous variable. The use is consistent with many academic studies and financial models such as the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM), Fama-French three and five factor models and many others. Again, the DAR reflects both market valuation and income expectations, which are influenced by macroeconomic factors like interest rates and inflation. DAR includes both capital gains/losses and dividends, offering a comprehensive view of investor earnings on the investment and provides additional advantage especially for investors who care about total wealth and not just price appreciation.

Macroeconomic factors are broad economic indicators that reflect the overall health and direction of a nation's economy, influencing financial markets, business performance, and investor behaviour. Variables such as interest rates, inflation, and exchange rates are shaped by government policies and global conditions, and they play a crucial role in determining stock market outcomes. Scholars such as Mankiw (2019) and Blanchard & Johnson (2017) described macroeconomic factors as aggregate forces that affect national income, price levels, and employment, while Bybee et al. (2023) emphasized that macroeconomic narratives act as systematic risk factors that influence asset pricing, reinforcing the foundational view of macroeconomic risk in financial markets. In emerging markets like Nigeria, where economic volatility is more pronounced, understanding the impact of these macroeconomic indicators is essential for evaluating stock returns and guiding investment decisions.

Stock returns, in particular, are influenced by a complex interplay of macroeconomic variables that reflect the broader economic environment. Across developed and emerging economies, factors such as interest rates, inflation rate, and exchange rates have consistently shaped market performance, guiding investment decisions and portfolio strategies. Numerous empirical studies have explored these relationships, revealing that macroeconomic stability is often a prerequisite for sustained capital market growth. However, the nature and strength of these effects vary significantly across regions, depending on institutional frameworks, market efficiency, and investor behaviour.

Several empirical studies have explored the impact of macroeconomic factors on stock returns, particularly in emerging markets. Fama (1981) established a foundational link between inflation and stock returns, arguing that rising inflation erodes real returns and investor confidence. Interest rates have also been widely studied; Adekunle et al. (2024) found that higher interest rates tend to depress stock prices in Nigeria due to increased borrowing costs and reduced corporate profitability, reinforcing the traditional view of interest rate-stock market dynamics. Exchange rate volatility presents another critical dimension. Adekunle (2024) posited that currency depreciation can negatively affect firms with foreign exposure, thereby influencing stock performance in Nigeria's capital market. Still within the Nigerian context, Akpa (2023) observed that fluctuations in interest and exchange rates significantly affect market capitalization and investor sentiment, reinforcing earlier findings on macroeconomic volatility and market dynamics. These studies collectively underscored the importance of macroeconomic stability in fostering a conducive environment for stock market growth and firm-level performance.

While these global insights provided a useful framework, the Nigerian context presents unique

conditions that necessitate localized investigation. The Nigeria's economy is characterized by high inflation volatility, frequent monetary policy shifts, and persistent exchange rate instability, factors that often amplify market uncertainty and investor risk aversion. Unlike more developed markets, the transmission of macroeconomic shocks to the stock market in Nigeria is influenced by structural inefficiencies, limited financial literacy, and a relatively shallow capital market. Moreover, the Central Bank's interventions and the dual exchange rate regime further complicated the relationship between macroeconomic indicators and stock performance. These conditions underscored the importance of examining how interest rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate, within Nigeria's economic realities, impact the stock returns of quoted companies, offering insights that are both contextually relevant and policy-informing.

Despite the theoretical and empirical relevance of macroeconomic factors, recent literature continued to produce mixed and sometimes contradictory findings regarding their impact on stock returns. For instance, Evbayiro-Osagie et al. (2024) found that interest rate and exchange rate significantly affected stock returns in Nigeria, recommending policy interventions to stabilize these variables. Conversely, Ordue et al. (2024) observed that while inflation and GDP had long-run positive effects on market performance, interest rate and exchange rate showed no significant short-term influence. Similarly, Elijah et al. (2025) reported that interest rate and external debt negatively impacted stock market performance, while exchange rate and money supply had positive long-run effects. These inconsistencies highlighted the need for context-specific research that reflects Nigeria's unique economic structure and policy environment. Again, while several studies have examined macroeconomic variables individually, few have jointly analyzed interest rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate using robust methodologies

tailored to Nigeria's market. This study, whose main objective is to evaluate the effect of macroeconomic factors on the stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria, seeks to fill these identified gaps by addressing all these dimensions. Specifically, the study also intends to determine the respective effect of interest rate, inflation rate and exchange rate on stock returns of quoted firms in Nigeria. The findings are expected to offer practical insights for investors seeking to optimize their portfolios, corporate managers aiming to enhance firm value, and policymakers working to improve market efficiency and transparency.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

▪ Stock Returns

Stock returns represent the gains or losses realized by investors from holding equity securities over a given period, typically expressed as a percentage of the initial investment. In recent times, scholars defined stock returns not only as a measure of profitability but also as a reflection of market sentiment and firm performance. According to Elijah et al. (2025), stock returns serve as a key indicator of investor confidence and are influenced by both firm-specific and macroeconomic factors. Evbayiro-Osagie et al. (2024) emphasized that stock returns encapsulated the combined effect of price appreciation and dividend income, making them a comprehensive metric for evaluating financial performance. Ordue et al. (2024) further argued that, in emerging markets like Nigeria, stock returns are particularly sensitive to economic volatility, policy shifts, and currency fluctuations, underscoring their role as a barometer of economic stability and investment attractiveness. These perspectives highlighted stock returns as a multidimensional concept central to financial analysis, portfolio management, and market forecasting.

▪ Macroeconomic Factors

Recent studies have shown the central role of macroeconomic factors in shaping financial market performance. Abaidoo and Agyapong (2024) defined macroeconomic factors as aggregate indicators such as inflation, interest rates, exchange rate and GDP that reflect the overall health and direction of an economy. Olayemi and Ojo (2024) also affirmed that macroeconomic indicators are critical drivers of financial market performance, investor behaviour, and national economic outcomes. In the context of financial markets, macroeconomic factors are viewed as external forces that affect asset pricing and investor sentiment, particularly in volatile economies. Elijah et al. (2025) thus described them as systemic variables that transmit economic shocks into the capital market, influencing stock returns through channels like monetary policy and exchange rate dynamics. These definitions and scholarly views underscored the importance of understanding macroeconomic indicators not just as statistical measures, but as strategic tools for evaluating market performance and guiding investment decisions, especially in emerging economies like Nigeria.

▪ Interest Rate

Interest rate is widely defined as the cost of borrowing or the reward for saving, and it plays a central role in shaping macroeconomic outcomes and financial market behaviour. According to Mishkin and Eakins (2021), interest rates serve as a key tool for allocating capital efficiently across sectors, influencing consumption, investment, and inflation. In emerging markets, interest rate movements are particularly impactful due to their role in signaling monetary policy direction and affecting investor sentiment (Adeniran et al., 2023). Olayemi and Okonkwo (2022) emphasized that interest rate volatility in Nigeria often reflected broader economic instability, making it a critical variable in stock market

analysis. Furthermore, Afolabi and Oduwole (2024) opined that interest rate changes directly affected corporate financing costs and portfolio rebalancing, thereby influencing stock returns.

▪ **Inflation Rate**

Inflation rate is broadly defined as the percentage change in the general price level of goods and services over time, reflecting shifts in purchasing power and economic stability. According to Obadan (2022), inflation is a critical macroeconomic indicator that influences investment decisions, cost structures, and consumer behaviour, especially in developing economies. Adebayo and Olayemi (2023) averred that inflation affects stock returns by altering real income and discount rates, thereby impacting asset valuation and investor expectations. In the Nigerian context, Bello and Salawu (2024) emphasized that inflation is often driven by supply-side constraints, exchange rate volatility, and fiscal imbalances, making it a persistent challenge for monetary authorities and financial market participants. Furthermore, Eze and Okafor (2023) highlighted that high and unpredictable inflation undermines investor confidence and distorts capital allocation, reinforcing its role as a key variable in financial modeling and macroeconomic analysis.

▪ **Exchange Rate**

Exchange rate is defined as the value of one currency relative to another, and it plays a vital role in shaping trade flows, investment decisions, and macroeconomic stability. According to Oputa and Nwankwo (2023), exchange rate serves as a key determinant of external competitiveness, influencing the cost of imports and exports and thereby affecting corporate profitability and market performance. In the Nigerian context, Akinyemi and Ojo (2024) reported that exchange rate fluctuations, often driven by oil price volatility and monetary policy shifts, have a direct impact on investor

confidence and stock market behaviour while Uche and Ibrahim (2022) emphasized that exchange rate instability increases uncertainty in financial markets, leading to higher risk premiums and reduced foreign portfolio inflows. Furthermore, Okonkwo and Eze (2023) highlighted that exchange rate movements affect inflation and interest rates, reinforcing its role as a transmission channel for macroeconomic shocks.

• **Empirical Review**

Empirical studies have been conducted to assess the influence of interest rate on stock returns across various economies, with findings revealing both consistent and conflicting outcomes. Akinyemi and Ojo (2024), Evbayiro-Osagie et al. (2024), Putra and Rahmi (2024), Shakir and Adekunle (2024), Msindo (2023) and Olayemi and Okonkwo (2022) found a significant negative relationship between interest rate and stock returns, suggesting that rising interest rates increase borrowing costs and reduce corporate profitability, thereby dampening investor enthusiasm. Similarly, Adeniran et al. (2023) observed that higher interest rates tend to shift investor preference toward fixed-income securities, leading to reduced demand for equities. However, contrasting evidence were presented by Elijah et al. (2025), Ahmad et al. (2024), Ordue et al. (2024) and Akwe et al. (2018) who reported either weak or statistically insignificant relationships between interest rate and stock returns, implying that other macroeconomic variables or market inefficiencies may dilute the expected impact. The conclusion of Gu et al. (2021) presented a time varying dimension in which interest rate initially exhibited a significant negative relationship with stock returns but overtime changed to a significant positive relationship. In a very unique finding, Bibek (2023) established a positive relationship between bank rate and stock returns indicating

that when the bank rate increases, stock returns also increase, the situation considered unusual because traditional financial theory often predicts the opposite.

Empirical research continued to explore the relationship between inflation rate and stock returns across various economies, with findings revealing both consistent and conflicting outcomes. Afolabi and Oduwole (2024), Ahmad et al. (2024), Ahuja (2024), Sahu (2024), Folorunso (2023) and Suharyanto and Zaki (2021) found a significant negative relationship, suggesting that rising inflation erodes purchasing power and investor confidence, thereby reducing equity demand. However, Okonkwo and Eze (2023), Ogiemudia et al. (2022) and Garg et al. (2021) observed a weak and statistically insignificant relationship, arguing that inflation's impact may be offset by other macroeconomic variables or delayed policy responses. Karagoz (2024) presented a mixed but sector-based outcomes. While some sectors exhibited a negative effect, other sectors showed a positive correlation. In another mixed but economy-based results, Sathyanarayana and Gargesa (2018) concluded that inflation had a significant negative effect in some countries while others exhibited positive relationship. Noruwa (2024) presented yet another complex and mixed relationship. In the short-run, inflation and stock returns exhibited a significant negative relationship while in the long-run the effect was positive.

Empirical investigations into the relationship between exchange rate and stock returns continued to yield mixed results, across different economies including that of Nigeria. Arikewuyo (2024), Wang (2024), Adaramola et al. (2023), Gbadebo (2023) and Chen and Liu (2021) found a significant negative relationship between exchange rate and stock price movement, with causality flowing from exchange rate to stock prices. Their findings suggested that currency depreciation negatively affected firm

performance, especially in sectors reliant on imports. Effe-Nnamdi et al. (2025) also reported that exchange rate depreciation contributed to investor uncertainty and amplified stock market volatility, although the direct impact on returns was statistically insignificant. Similarly, Adekunle et al. (2024) and Adeniyi and Kumeka (2019) reported no significant relationship of stock returns with exchange rate changes, arguing that Nigeria's fragmented exchange rate regime and limited foreign investor participation might have weakened the transmission mechanism. In direct contrast to the aforementioned studies, Ogbodo et al. (2024), El-Diftar (2023) and Okechukwu et al. (2019) reported a significant positive relationship indicating that stock returns rise when domestic currency depreciates relative to foreign currencies.

Based on above conceptual review, the following hypotheses were formulated.

H₀₋₁: Interest Rate has no significant effect on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria.

H₀₋₂: Inflation Rate has no significant effect on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria.

H₀₋₃: Exchange rate has no significant effect on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria.

▪ **Efficient Market Hypothesis**

This study was anchored on the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH), originally proposed by Eugene Fama in his ground-breaking 1970 paper. EMH posited that financial markets are "informationally efficient," meaning that asset prices fully reflect all available information at any given time. According to this theory, it is impossible for investors to consistently achieve returns above the market average through either technical analysis or fundamental analysis, because any new information is rapidly incorporated into stock prices. EMH is categorized into three forms; weak, semi-strong, and strong, each reflecting different levels of

market efficiency based on the type of information absorbed. Critics of EMH argued that it oversimplified investor behaviour, ignored psychological and irrational market dynamics, and failed to account for anomalies such as bubbles and crashes. Nonetheless, EMH remained a foundational theory in financial economics, particularly in studies examining the relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock market performance. In the context of this study, macroeconomic factors such as inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, and GDP growth are considered public information that should be instantly priced into the stock market if the Nigerian market is efficient. EMH thus provided a robust framework to assess whether changes in these macroeconomic indicators have a predictable and measurable impact on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quantitative longitudinal research design, specifically utilizing an ex post facto and correlational approach. This design was appropriate because it relied on historical data to examine the relationship between macroeconomic variables; interest rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate, and stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria. The ex post facto aspect allowed for analysis of existing data without manipulation, while the correlational component facilitated the assessment of statistical associations among the variables. Time-series data spanning ten years were employed to capture trends and dynamic interactions, using Least Square Regression model to evaluate the impact of macroeconomic factors on stock performance.

The population of the study comprised all the quoted companies on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) on or before 2014. These companies were ranked from top to bottom based on their market capitalization as at 31st December

2024. Twenty-seven (27) top companies were selected using purposive sampling technique based on the set criteria. The criteria were to ensure availability of consistent data for the ten-year period (2015–2024) required for robust data analysis. Data deployed in this study were exclusively secondary in nature. The secondary data were collated from multiple sources. Data on the macroeconomic factors were sourced from the archives and publications of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS). Data on stock returns were sourced from the published annual financial statements and reports of the sampled firms. The selected companies cut across different sectors of the Nigerian economy.

Model Specification

$$SR_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 IntR_t + \beta_2 InfR_t + \beta_3 ExcR_t + \mu_t$$

where:

SR represents Stock Returns measured by Dividend-Adjusted Returns (DAR);

IntR represents Interest Rate measured by CBN Prime Lending Rate (PLR);

InfR represents Inflation Rate measured by the CBN Inflation Rate (YoY);

ExcR represents Exchange Rate measured by the NGN/USD Exchange Rate;

α represents the constant;

β_1, β_3 represent the coefficients of the explanatory variables;

μ represents the error term;

t represents the time series effect.

Variables	Proxy	Description	Reference
Stock Returns	Dividend-Adjusted Returns (DAR)	$\frac{[A - B] + C}{B}$ A=Current month share price B=Last month share price C=Dividend	BLiu et al. (2023), Roussanov & Lopez-lira (2023), Malhotra et al. (2023)
Interest Rate	Prime Lending Rate (PLR)	Central Bank of Nigeria's benchmark interest rate	Peter et al. (2024), Akwe (2013), Okechukwu et al. (2019)
Inflation Rate	YoY Inflation	Year on Year inflation rate set by the CBN which measure % change in CPI	Peter et al. (2024), Akwe (2013), Okechukwu et al. (2019)
Exchange Rate	Naira/USD	Natural logarithm of Naira to US Dollar	Okechukwu et al. (2019)

Source: Author's compilation 2025

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings from this study are presented in tables for clarity and easy understanding.

TABLE 2: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

	DAR	INTR	INFR	EXCR
Mean	0.096044	15.11475	16.97650	6.009507
Median	0.087506	15.95083	16.08625	5.915246
Maximum	0.448120	17.55333	31.56667	7.279610
Minimum	-0.104848	11.48333	9.010000	5.287764
Std. Dev.	0.080480	2.069246	6.392840	0.511437
Skewness	0.851680	-0.518026	1.036238	1.218807
Kurtosis	4.529534	1.747938	3.276072	4.352717
Jarque-Bera	58.96027	29.71198	49.17793	87.43284
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	25.93177	4080.982	4583.655	1622.567
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.742341	1151.799	10993.60	70.36171
Observations	270	270	270	270

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

The average DAR of 0.0960 suggested a moderately profitable stock market environment in Nigeria, with a standard deviation of 0.0805 indicating moderate volatility and a leptokurtic distribution (kurtosis = 4.53), implying frequent extreme market movements. INTR averaged 15.11% with modest variability (SD = 2.07), a negative skewness (-0.52), and a platykurtic shape (kurtosis = 1.75), reflecting relatively stable but high borrowing costs.

INFR showed a high mean of 16.98% and a wide spread (SD = 6.39), with positive skewness (1.04) and slight leptokurtosis (kurtosis = 3.28), indicating frequent inflationary spikes. EXCR, log-transformed, had a mean of 6.01 and SD of 0.51, with skewness (1.22) and kurtosis (4.35) suggesting recurring exchange rate shocks. These patterns highlighted the volatility and asymmetry of Nigeria’s macroeconomic environment and its implications for stock market performance.

TABLE 3: CORRELATION MATRIX TABLE

Covariance Analysis: Ordinary				
Date: 11/08/25 Time: 19:12				
Sample: 1 270				
Included observations: 270				
Correlation Probability	DAR	INTR	INFR	EXCR
DAR	1.000000			
INTR	-0.178102	1.000000		
INFR	0.324405	-0.137946	1.000000	
EXCR	0.250809	-0.167219	0.911288	1.000000

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

The correlation analysis revealed linear relationships between dividend-adjusted returns (DAR) and key macroeconomic variables. Interest rate showed a negative and statistically significant correlation with DAR ($r = -0.1781$), confirming the inverse relationship predicted by the interest rate hypothesis, where rising rates reduce stock returns due to portfolio shifts toward fixed-income securities. Inflation rate exhibited a strong positive correlation with DAR ($r = 0.3244$), suggesting that nominal stock returns tend to rise with inflation, consistent with the Fisher Effect, although real returns may still be eroded. Exchange rate also had a positive and significant correlation with DAR ($r = 0.2508$), indicating that naira depreciation may enhance stock returns, particularly for export-oriented

firms and foreign investors. A very strong positive correlation between inflation and exchange rate ($r = 0.9113$) highlights the structural link between currency depreciation and inflationary pressures in Nigeria, supporting imported inflation theory. Meanwhile, interest rate showed weak negative correlations with both inflation ($r = -0.1379$) and exchange rate ($r = -0.1672$), reflecting partial monetary policy effectiveness. These relationships underscore the interconnected nature of macroeconomic variables in shaping stock market performance and suggest that inflation and exchange rate movements may offer nominal gains, while interest rate hikes tend to depress equity valuations.

TABLE 4: BREUSCH-PAGAN/COOK-WEISBERG TEST FOR HETEROSKEDASTICITY

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity			
F-statistic	2.409815	Prob. F(3, 266)	0.0674
Obs*R-squared	7.143996	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.0674
Scaled explained SS	12.88968	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.0049

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey (BPG) heteroskedasticity test affirmed that the residuals of the regression model exhibited constant variance, supporting the assumption of homoskedasticity. The study therefore failed to reject the null hypothesis. The results thus validated the robustness of the regression model, indicating that the estimated relationships between interest rate, inflation, and exchange

rate with dividend-adjusted returns are statistically reliable and not distorted by unequal variances in the residuals. This supports the overall conclusion that the model provided a credible basis for assessing the sensitivity of Nigeria’s stock market performance to key macroeconomic variables.

TABLE 5: RAMSEY REGRESSION EQUATION SPECIFICATION ERROR TEST (RESET)

Ramsey RESET Test			
Equation: UNTITLED			
Omitted Variables: Squares of fitted values			
Specification: DAR INTR INFR EXCR C			
	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	1.077733	265	0.2821
F-statistic	1.161509	(1, 265)	0.2821
Likelihood ratio	1.180839	1	0.2772

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

The Ramsey RESET test was employed to assess whether the regression model examining the impact of interest rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate on dividend-adjusted returns (DAR) in Nigeria was correctly specified. The test checks for specification errors such as omitted variables or incorrect functional form. Results showed a t-statistic of 1.0777 (p = 0.2821), F-statistic of 1.1615 (p = 0.2821), and LR value of 1.1808 (p = 0.2772), all exceeding

the 5% significance level. This represents failure to reject the null hypothesis, confirming that the model is appropriately specified with no significant nonlinearities or omitted variables. The minimal difference between restricted and unrestricted sum of squares further supported the adequacy of the linear functional form, suggesting that the model sufficiently captured the relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock returns.

TABLE 6: REGRESSION RESULTS

Dependent Variable: DAR
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 11/08/25 Time: 19:13
 Sample: 1 270
 Included observations: 270

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INTR	-0.005782	0.002246	-2.573908	0.0106
INFR	0.007276	0.001741	4.179132	0.0000
EXCR	-0.047322	0.021862	-2.164610	0.0313
C	0.344301	0.114368	3.010460	0.0029
R-squared	0.138541	Mean dependent var		0.096044
Adjusted R-squared	0.128825	S.D. dependent var		0.080480
S.E. of regression	0.075118	Akaike info criterion		-2.324813
Sum squared resid	1.500956	Schwarz criterion		-2.271503
Log likelihood	317.8498	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.303406
F-statistic	14.25945	Durbin-Watson stat		1.413792
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

The results of least square regression provided a comprehensive view of the dynamic relationships among dividend-adjusted returns (DAR) and key macroeconomic variables: interest rate (INTR), inflation rate (INFR), and exchange rate (EXCR) in Nigeria. The dataset included 270 observations from 27 listed Nigerian companies over a ten-year period.

▪ **Interest Rate (INTR):**

The regression analysis revealed a negative and statistically significant relationship between interest rate and dividend-adjusted returns (DAR). With a coefficient of -0.0058 and a p-value of 0.0106 , the result indicated that a one-unit increase in interest rate leads to a 0.0058 decrease in stock returns. This finding supported the interest rate hypothesis and opportunity cost theory, suggesting that higher interest rates make fixed-income securities more attractive, prompting investors to shift away from equities. The outcome aligned with prior studies showing that elevated borrowing costs and reduced corporate profitability under high interest rate

regimes tend to depress stock market performance in Nigeria. The finding was consistent with Akinyemi and Ojo (2024), Evbayiro-Osagie et al. (2024), Putra and Rahmi (2024) and Shakir and Adekunle (2024).

▪ **Inflation Rate (INFR):**

Inflation demonstrated a positive and highly significant effect on stock returns, with a coefficient of 0.0073 and a p-value of 0.0000 . This implied that a one-unit rise in inflation corresponds to a 0.0073 increase in dividend-adjusted returns. The result supported the Fisher Effect, which posited that nominal returns rise with inflation as investors seek compensation for diminished purchasing power. In the Nigerian context, this suggests that firms may have successfully passed inflationary costs to consumers, preserving nominal earnings and dividends. Speculative trading during inflationary periods may also have contributed to short-term gains in equity returns. The finding was consistent with Karagoz (2024), Sathyanarayana and Gargesa (2018) and Noruwa (2024).

▪ **Exchange Rate (EXCR):**

The exchange rate exhibited a negative and statistically significant impact on stock returns, with a coefficient of -0.0473 and a p-value of 0.0313 . This indicated that a one-unit increase in the exchange rate (reflecting naira depreciation), results in a 0.0473 decline in dividend-adjusted returns. The finding suggested that currency instability undermines investor confidence, increases import costs, and discourages foreign portfolio investment. While short-term speculative gains may occur, sustained depreciation tends to erode market performance. This outcome is consistent with the Exchange Rate Pass-Through Hypothesis and highlights the vulnerability of Nigeria's stock market to exchange rate volatility. The finding was consistent with Arikewuyo (2024), Wang (2024), Adaramola et al. (2023), Gbadebo (2023).

▪ **Result of Granger Causality Tests**

The VAR Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Tests (appendix 1) were conducted to determine whether past values of macroeconomic variables; interest rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate, can predict dividend-adjusted stock returns (DAR) in Nigeria, and vice versa. The results showed that all the three macroeconomic factors significantly Granger-caused DAR, confirming their predictive relevance for stock market performance. Additionally, DAR, inflation, and exchange rate also significantly influenced interest rate movements, while inflation was driven by interest rate and exchange rate dynamics, and exchange rate was primarily shaped by monetary and inflationary factors. These findings revealed a complex web of bidirectional and unidirectional causality, highlighting the interconnected nature of Nigeria's financial and macroeconomic systems and emphasizing the need for integrated policy and investment strategies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the dynamic relationship between macroeconomic variables; interest rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate, and dividend-adjusted stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, least square regression model and Granger causality tests. The results revealed an interesting and content specific relationship between macroeconomic factors and stock returns of listed firms in Nigeria. Interest rate had a negative and significant effect on DAR suggesting that rising rates reduce stock returns due to increased borrowing costs and portfolio shifts toward fixed-income assets. Inflation showed a positive and highly significant impact implying that moderate inflation boosts nominal returns, likely through price adjustments and speculative trading. Exchange rate depreciation negatively affected DAR reflecting investor uncertainty, higher import costs, and reduced foreign investment.

The study concluded that Nigeria's stock market returns are significantly influenced by macroeconomic conditions. Specifically, rising interest rates and exchange rate depreciation exert downward pressure on stock performance, while moderate inflation contributes positively in the short run. These findings underscored the sensitivity of equity returns to monetary and exchange rate policies, highlighting the importance of macroeconomic stability for investor confidence and market growth. Although the model's explanatory power was modest, it reflected the complex and multifactorial nature of financial markets in emerging economies.

Based on these findings, the null hypotheses in the three cases were rejected. Thus, the results demonstrated that macroeconomic variables played a significant predictive role in determining dividend-adjusted stock returns in Nigeria, and there exists a reciprocal relationship between

stock market performance and monetary and exchange rate dynamics. These interactions underscored the importance of integrating macroeconomic analysis with financial market monitoring for both investment decision-making and policy formulation.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were suggested for investors, policymakers, regulators, and stakeholders in the diverse sectors of the Nigerian economy.

1. The Central Bank of Nigeria should adopt a balanced interest rate policy that supports economic stability without stifling equity market growth. Excessively high rates discourage investment and reduce corporate profitability, leading to weaker stock returns. Investors should adopt a dynamic strategy that accounts for the timing of monetary policy shifts. Listed companies should also monitor interest rate trends to optimize financing decisions and mitigate the cost of capital.
2. While moderate inflation may enhance nominal returns, persistent inflation undermines real investment value. The Central Bank of Nigeria should maintain inflation within an optimal band through proactive monetary and fiscal coordination to preserve investor purchasing power and market stability. Investors should be cautious during inflationary periods, as rising prices erode real returns and increase market uncertainty. Firms should focus on cost management and operational efficiency to maintain profitability under inflationary pressure.
3. Given the negative impact of exchange rate depreciation on stock returns, efforts should be made to reduce currency volatility. Transparent and consistent exchange rate policies can help attract

foreign investment and support market resilience. Investors should factor currency risk into their valuation models and consider exposure to export-oriented firms that benefit from naira depreciation. Listed companies with foreign operations or import dependencies should adopt currency risk management practices, such as hedging and diversification, to cushion the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on performance.

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